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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternate Current
AFE	Active Front End
AKF	Adaptive Kalman Filter
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CIGRE	Conseil International des Grands Réseaux Électriques
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DC	Direct Current
DCT	DC transformer
DESL	Distributed Electrical System Laboratory
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DKF	Discrete Kalman Filter
DMU	DC Measurement Unit
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
EV	Electric Vehicle
FACTS	Flexible AC transmission system
GPS	Global Positioning System
HVDC	High Voltage DC
IGBT	Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor
KF	Kalman Filter
LAN	Local Area Network
LNR	Largest Normalized Residual
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MPP	Maximum Power Point
OPF	Optimal Power Flow
PDC	Phasor Data Concentrator
PECE	Prediction Error Covariance Estimation
PEL	Power Electronics Laboratory
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RMS	Root Mean Square
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RT	Real-Time
RTU	Remote Terminal Unit
SC	Sensitivity Coefficients
SE	State Estimator
TNR	True Negative Ratio
TPR	True Positive Ratio
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
WLS	Weighted Least Squares

Executive Summary

Hybrid AC/DC grids are a promising solution to increase the share of distributed generation in future power grids that are expected to massively rely on stochastic renewable power generation. Indeed, combining AC and DC systems creates the opportunity for more flexible control and increased system efficiency (Eghtedarpour & Farjah, 2014a).

This report summarises the progress and results achieved by EPFL in Task T6.1 of HYPERRIDE. The aim is to study the Optimal Power Flow (OPF)-based grid-aware control problem in hybrid AC/DC grids, targeting different objectives associated with the stochastic nature of the available resources.

The technical report defines and explains in detail the methodology for the implementation of optimal control in hybrid AC/DC networks. First, the distributed sensing infrastructure and the associated situational awareness system are described. It consists of PMU and DMU that measure time-tagged voltages and currents synchronised by the Universal Time Coordinated (UTC)-Global Positioning System (GPS) reference signal. The Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC) collects and time-aligns the measurements and streams them to the SE. For the HYPERRIDE project, a linear and exact state estimation measurement model is developed that relates the measurements to the states and allows for a computationally efficient real-time SE. The updated state estimates (computed at a rate of 20 ms) are streamed to the centralised controller that performs an OPF-based algorithm in real-time to compute the optimal setpoints for the controllable resources (i.e. PV, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Super Capacitors, AC/DC AFE). A linear OPF algorithm based on the sensitivity coefficients is proposed for the optimal control of the hybrid network. Therefore, an analytical method is developed to analytically compute the partial derivatives of the hybrid AC/DC power flow equations. Once the optimal setpoints are computed, the centralized controller streams the setpoints to each resource agent that is in direct communication with its resource.

Furthermore, the architecture, functionalities and commissioning of the main components of the hybrid microgrid are defined and realized by the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) DESL and the PEL. The above-introduced data acquisition and real-time SE are implemented on the EPFL's hybrid network and are experimentally validated.

1 Introduction

The aim of the Work Package 6 (WP06) of HYPERRIDE is to develop a laboratory setup of a hybrid low-voltage AC/DC microgrid to investigate the performance, benefits and drawbacks of such grid configuration, as well as to develop guidelines for grid planning and operation, by testing optimal control strategies and adaptive topology reconfiguration approaches.

Task T6.1 studies the AC/DC OPF-based grid-aware control fed by distributed and synchronized measurements (PMUs and DMUs). This technical document describes the theoretical developments and results of the OPF-based control for hybrid AC/DC networks.

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

Microgrids are a promising solution to increase the share of distributed generation in future power grids that are expected to massively rely on renewable power generation. However, microgrids cannot be treated or controlled in the identical way as conventional power systems. They have several fundamental different key characteristics that create challenges for their optimal control and, ultimately, their stability, namely: the high penetration of RES interfaced by power electronics results in lower system inertia and increases the uncertainty in the system's dynamic response. The lower reactance-to-resistance ratio of the branch impedances prevents the decoupling of active and reactive power flows, which leads to a strong linkage between voltage and frequency controls (usually decoupled in high voltage transmission systems). The loading in microgrids is typically unbalanced, which is an additional issue when the microgrid operates in isolated (or islanded) mode since the system's voltage and frequency are no longer supported by the upstream utility grid.

To cope with the above-mentioned unfavourable characteristics, an emerging interest arises nowadays in hybrid AC/DC microgrids where conventional AC microgrids are interlinked with DC microgrids using VSC (Wang, Goel, Liu, & Choo, 2013) (Liu, Wang, & Loh, 2010). Additionally, Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and BESS often have a DC nature and can be directly interfaced with emerging DC loads, such as Electric Vehicle (EV) and variable-speed motor controllers. Indeed, combining AC and DC creates the opportunity for an increased system's efficiency because of the reduction of the number of conversion devices, more flexible control and can improve the system's stability (Eghtedarpour & Farjah, 2014a) (Liu et al., 2010).

The WP06 of HYPERRIDE aims at studying the development and the implementation of control strategies for hybrid AC/DC microgrids. Microgrid control exists at different layers, each operating on a different timescale. At the lowest layer are the resources (AFE converters, controllable PV, BESS, etc.) characterized by the fastest control loops operating at the millisecond timescale. These resources receive optimal setpoints from centralized grid-aware controllers (e.g. the intra-day control) that take the systems state into account and track the resource utilisation

Figure 1: Workflow of the different control layers and their time resolution.

profile. These profiles are generated by higher-level control loops usually operating at a time-scale of 24 h (e.g. the day ahead control). Figure 1 illustrates the different control layers and situates them on a common timescale.

Sensing

The emerging availability of PMUs provides synchronised measurements of the grid current and voltages at a rate of tens of frames per second. The PMUs adopted in this research use the enhanced interpolated Discrete Fourier Transform algorithm (e-IpDFT) to extract the phasor and frequency of nodal voltages and branch/nodal currents (Romano & Paolone, 2014). At the DC part of the system, DMUs provide synchronised measurements of the voltage and current quantities. The DMUs provide DC measurements at the same rate as their PMU counterpart, and use suitable low-pass filters in series with averaging blocks to filter out high-frequency components. The DMUs are implemented in a similar hardware, software and data stream protocol (e.g. IEEE C37.118) as the PMUs, to maximize compatibility with the already existing communication infrastructure.

State estimator

Measurements from the PMUs and DMUs are concentrated in the PDC and forwarded to the SE. Knowledge about the system's state is a requisite for several key functions, such as grid-aware optimal control, stability assessment and security (Paolone, Le Boudec, Sarri, & Zanni, 2015). SE in solely AC grids is a well-understood problem where the literature has provided several solutions relying on both static and recursive algorithms fed by both PMU and Remote Terminal Unit (RTU) measurements (Abur & Exposito, 2004). For hybrid AC/DC systems, instead, the SE still relies on different approximations as discussed in Section 3.2.

From a computational perspective, it is well known that only when the AC phasors are written in Cartesian coordinates the measurement model that relates the measurements to the states can be formulated in a strictly linear way. At the DC part of the system, the DC measurement model of a SE is intrinsically linear. The VSC model, linking the DC quantities to the complex AC phasors represented in Cartesian coordinates, however, does not intrinsically lead to a linear relationship between the states and the measurements. The VSC representation is, therefore, the key aspect in the SE of AC/DC grids.

In this respect, the first part of the deliverable introduces a method to create a fully linear measurement model for VSCs using the complex modulation index of the VSC that links the real and imaginary parts of the complex phasors at the AC side to the magnitude of the DC quantities. Using the symmetric component decomposition, the linear model is extended to unbalanced three-phase (3-ph) hybrid grids. For the activity in this task, we propose an exact recursive SE, relying on a Kalman Filter (KF) that uses a measurement model and the system's time evolution to estimate the unbiased and minimum variance states (Lambrichts & Paolone, 2022). The KF uses all available measurements, past and present and as shown in (Sarri, Zanni, Popovic, Le Boudec, & Paolone, 2016), it can be analytically proved that the estimation error of the KF is always lower than the estimation error of a static SE, provided that the KF process model hypotheses are correct. The choice of the KF relies on the nature of the proposed model in order to take into account the converter's losses that, as a matter of fact, does require the previously computed state making the SE problem inherently recursive. Details and hypotheses about this aspect are described in Appendix 5. Furthermore, the SE is coupled with a fast adaptive KF that updates the process model covariance matrix and is, therefore, highly suitable for step-varying states. The hybrid AC/DC grid defined above

is modelled and simulated within the EMTP-RV environment (the electromagnetic transients program (Mahseredjian, Lefebvre, & Do, 1993)(Mahseredjian, Denetière, Dubé, Khodabakhchian, & Gérin-Lajoie, 2007)) and is used to validate the SE numerically. An experimental validation on the hybrid microgrid at the EPFL is also presented. The developed analytical methods and numerical validation are published in (Lambrichts & Paolone, 2022) and included into this work package report.

Intra-day control

Microgrids are interfaced by controllable and uncontrollable units. The goal of the intra-day control is to operate these units in order to track, in general, a day-ahead computed trajectory (e.g. dispatch plan, self-consumption, etc.) as close as possible (Gupta, Sossan, & Paolone, 2020). The intra-day control may be formulated as a Model Predictive Control (MPC) problem with a time step of few seconds (e.g. 5s) and a receding horizon of few minutes (e.g. 5 to 15 min). The MPC uses the estimated states and the updated Distributed Energy Resource (DER) forecasts, to compute the optimal setpoints of all the controllable units in order to follow, as closely as possible, the day-ahead computed power trajectory. The MPC accounts for the grid constraints by including the power flow equations. The power flow constraints need to be suitably modified due to the hybrid nature of the grid. Indeed, the VSC needs to be accurately modelled and the DC power flow equations need to be included. The challenges here rise in the formulation and convexification or linearization of an AC/DC OPF problem. For this project, a novel analytical method is developed based on the concept of AC sensitivity coefficients. These are the partial derivatives of voltage with respect to the control variables and allow to formulate the grid constraints in a fully linear way, thus approximation the original AC OPF non-convex constraints.

Day ahead control

The day ahead control computes the next day optimal power trajectory of the aggregated microgrid resources for a certain time horizon. The considered horizon consists of 24 h with a resolution of 5 to 15 min. Using a day-ahead forecast of the DERs, the day-ahead control accounts for the availability of all the units and the grid constraints while still guaranteeing sufficient flexibility (Gupta et al., 2020). The dispatch problem for hybrid AC/DC grids is very similar to the conventional AC microgrid dispatch problem (Sossan, Namor, Cherkaoui, & Paolone, 2016).

1.2 Structure of the Document

The further report is structured as follows.

Section 2 introduces the characteristics of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid developed at the EPFL. Both, the electrical and the communication networks are presented. In section 3, the SE in hybrid AC/DC microgrids is discussed. A linear measurement model is proposed for the accurate, sub-second SE of hybrid AC/DC hybrid microgrids. A numerical and experimental validation of the SE for the hybrid microgrid introduced in section 3 is shown. Section 4 presents the OPF algorithm based on the sensitivity coefficients of the hybrid network. A new analytical method is developed and validated. It allows for the computation of the grids' sensitivity coefficients as a system of linear equations by using the knowledge of the systems state and its admittance matrix. A numerical experiment is included to demonstrate the use of the sensitivity coefficients. Section 5 provides the conclusion of the deliverable.

2 System Description

This section describes the architecture of the system and gives the specifications and parameters of the demonstrator developed at EPFL.

2.1 AC/DC Microgrid Network

The Swiss demonstrator at the EPFL is developed as a joint effort between the DESL and the PEL. This section describes the architecture of the system and gives the specifications and parameters of the demonstrator’s assets. The overall architecture of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid is presented in 2.

The microgrid is realised through the interconnection of an in forerunner projects AC microgrid developed at DESL (yellow subsystem in Figure 2) and of a DC microgrid developed at PEL in HYPERRIDE (blue subsystem in Figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic architecture of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid developed at EPFL.
 The yellow subsystem represents the AC microgrid realised at DESL.
 The blue subsystem represents the DC microgrid realised at PEL.
 The interconnection between the AC and the DC microgrid is realized through four AFE units, also realized at PEL.

The AC microgrid located at the DESL is a full-scale replica of the 14 nodes benchmark defined by the Task Force C6.04.02 of the Conseil International des Grands Réseaux Électriques (CIGRE). It is a three-phase low-voltage AC network operating at a 50Hz frequency with a rated line-to-line voltage of 400 V. This microgrid is equipped with PV sources, a BESS, a supercapacitor-based storage system, a fuel cell system, an electrolyzer, a charging station for EVs and load emulators. The lines that compose the AC microgrid are real (i.e. not emulated)

The DC microgrid developed at PEL is composed of four DC lines, each of which is interfaced with a different node of the AC microgrid through an AFE. The AFEs have a rated voltage of 750 V and are sized to transfer up to 45 kW. The four DC lines of the DC microgrid are also interfaced with each other through bidirectional DC/DC converters. Two DC/DC converters are composed by DC transformer (DCT) based on series resonant conversion, and one DC/DC converter is composed by a Dual Active Bridge (DAB). By varying the voltage at the output of the AFEs, in the range [720 V; 780 V], a power flow through the DC/DC converters is regulated. This allows the supervisory grid controller to implement optimal power flow strategies within the hybrid AC/DC microgrid. Additionally, PV emulators are included in the architecture of the DC microgrid and are interfaced with the four DC lines to emulate a stochastic energy generation. Additionally, a supercapacitor-based storage system is also planned to be part of the DC microgrid. The DC side of the lines and the connection nodes of the DC/DC converters are equipped with DMUs to provide information to the supervisory grid controller.

At the present state, the four AFEs and the two DCTs have been realized and commissioned. Four low-power PV emulators have been realized and tested, but they have not been included in the DC microgrid, yet. The DAB unit and the supercapacitor-based storage system are currently under development. The report of Task 6.4 describes in detail the commissioning and testing of the AFE units, the DCT units, and the PV emulators. It also provides some preliminary results of the DC microgrid operation, obtained by connecting together the aforementioned units.

2.2 AC/DC Microgrid Communication

In parallel with the physical electrical network lays the communication layer. It consists of two sub-layers: the sensing and the control layers.

2.2.1 Sensing Layer

The sensing layer consists of PMUs and DMUs connected in a private Local Area Network (LAN) and provide time-aligned measurements. The measurement devices stream time-tagged and aligned measurements to the PDC that creates an array of time-aligned measurements. This array is streamed to the real-time SE that is illustrated in detail in Section 3.

2.2.2 Control Layer

Once the most likelihood state is computed and the centralised OPF has been performed, the optimal setpoints of the controllable resources have to be streamed to each resource. Since each resource has been purchased from different manufacturers (or custom build for the microgrid), each resource communicates through its own protocol. Therefore, a resource agent has been deployed for each resource in order to translate and send data to and from the central controller using its specific communication protocol. A graphical schematic of the communication layer is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Communication layer for the hybrid AC/DC microgrid.

3 Real-Time State Estimation of Hybrid AC/DC Grids

3.1 Introduction

The knowledge of the system's state is a prerequisite for several key operational and control processes, such as grid-aware OPF-driven control (Gupta et al., 2020), stability assessment, security and post-contingency analysis (Paolone et al., 2015). SE in solely AC grids, both static and recursive, is a well-understood problem where the literature has provided several solutions (Abur & Exposito, 2004). For hybrid AC/DC systems, instead, the SE still relies on different approximations as discussed in Section 3.2.

The emerging availability of PMUs provides synchronised measurements of the AC grid's current and voltage phasors at a rate of tens of frames per second ("IEEE Standard for Synchrophasor Measurements for Power Systems", 2011a). Only when these phasors are written in Cartesian coordinates, the measurement model that relates the measurements to the states can be formulated in a strictly linear way. At the DC part of the system, DMUs may also provide synchronised measurements. The DC measurement model of a SE is intrinsically linear. The VSC model, however, linking the DC quantities to the complex AC phasors represented in Cartesian coordinates, does not intrinsically lead to a linear relationship between the states and the measurements. The VSC representation is, therefore, the key aspect in SE of AC/DC grids.

In this respect, this chapter introduces a method to create a fully linear measurement model for VSCs using the complex modulation index of the VSC that links the real and imaginary parts of the complex phasors to the magnitude of the DC quantities. Using the symmetric component decomposition, the linear model is extended to unbalanced three-phase (3-ph) hybrid grids.

This chapter proposes an exact recursive SE, relying on a KF that uses a measurement model and the system's time evolution to estimate the unbiased and minimum variance states (Paolone et al., 2015). As known, the KF uses all available measurements, past and present and it can be analytically proved that the estimation error of the KF is always lower than the estimation error of a static SE, provided that the KF process model hypotheses are correct (Sarri et al., 2016). The choice of the KF relies on the nature of the model we propose to take into account the converter's losses that, as a matter of fact, do require the previously computed state making the SE problem inherently recursive. Details and hypotheses about this aspect are described in the Appendix 5. Furthermore, the SE is coupled with fast adaptive updates of the process model covariance matrix and is, therefore, highly suitable for step-varying states. Bad data in the AC and DC parts of the system are identified and rejected using the standard Largest Normalized Residual (LNR) test.

The CIGRE benchmark 14-node AC micro-grid defined by Task Force C6.04.02 (Barsali, Strunz, & Styczynski, 2005) is used to validate the SE. This benchmark grid is connected in 4 nodes to an 8-node DC grid using VSCs. The AC/DC hybrid grid is modelled and simulated in EMTP-RV. Within the context of the European project HYPERRIDE, the SE will be implemented into a real hybrid AC/DC micro-grid hosted at the DESL at the EPFL. This real-life hybrid network requires updated state estimates in a fast (i.e. sub-second) and accurate way for different real-time grid-aware optimal control algorithms. The real system's topology and location of the PMUs and DMUs are identical to the ones used in the simulation for the validation of the state estimation.

The section is structured as follows: Section 3.2 consists of a literature review on the SE of hybrid AC/DC networks, the transformer-like VSC model in the time domain and discusses the adaptive KF that uses the Prediction Error Covariance Estimation (PECE) method to assess the process model error distribution. Section 3.3 presents the fully linear measurement model for lossless and lossy VSCs. Section 3.4 describes the linear SE with bad data identification and an approximation of the PECE method. In Section 3.5, the hybrid SE algorithm is validated in the EMTP-RV simulation environment and its performance is compared with a non-linear WLS SE. Section 3.6 presents the experimental validation of the proposed method on the EPFL hybrid AC/DC network. The conclusions are given in Section 3.7.

The technical contributions and innovations of this work include: 1) proposition of an exact and fully linear hybrid AC/DC network measurement model that includes the interfacing AC/DC converter losses; 2) proposition of a computationally-efficient approximation of the Kalman filter PECE process proposed in (Zanni, Le Boudec, Cherkaoui, & Paolone, 2016); 3) a recursive state estimator for hybrid AC/DC micro-grids capable to track the system's state step changes including bad data detection and identification.

This chapter is based on the IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid paper (Lambrichts & Paolone, 2022) that originally proposes the linear and exact recursive state estimator.

3.2 State of the Art

3.2.1 State Estimation for Hybrid AC/DC Grids

The first applications of SE for hybrid AC/DC grids refer to High Voltage DC (HVDC) lines and Flexible AC transmission system (FACTS). Reference (de la Villa Jaén, Acha, & Expósito, 2008) describes a WLS SE for HVDC. A non-linear model of the VSC is used to link the AC system with the DC system using two relations: 1) the converter control inputs, namely the reference voltage magnitude and angle and 2) the power balance equations accounting for converter losses. (W. Li & Vanfretti, 2014) and (Khazraj, da Silva, & Bak, 2016) describe a solution for a linear SE for thyristor-based VSCs. Their solution consists of using the product of the voltage magnitude with the cosine of the firing angle and the excitation angle as state variables for the rectifier and inverter side. This approach makes the problem linear, however, its use is limited to only thyristor-based VSCs. Furthermore, this solution ignores converter losses. Other works incorporate the DC measurements using the non-linear power balance equations and use the modulation index as a measurement to link the DC voltage to the AC voltage magnitude (Mouco & Abur, 2017). (Zamora-Cárdenas, Fuerte-Esquivel, Pizano-Martinez, & Estrada-García, 2016) uses the power balance while ignoring the converter losses and iteratively solves the WLS SE using the partial derivative of the measurement equations.

When it comes to hybrid AC/DC grids with multiple DC links and an actual DC grid, fewer solutions have been proposed in the literature. (Xia, Gooi, Chen, & Hu, 2016) introduces a decentralised iterative technique that decomposes the SE problem of hybrid microgrids. The authors suggest first to formulate the SE of the AC and DC part separately and subsequently, solving it alternated in an optimisation problem using the lossy active power balance to link the two systems. (Kong, Yan, Guo, Xu, & Fang, 2018) and (Ping, Xiangrui, Chen, & Zheng, 2019) follow a similar approach to solve the hybrid SE problem. (Fang et al., 2021) accurately models the conduction and switching losses of the AC/DC interfacing converter. However, this SE still relies on a non-linear VSC model. In (W. Li, Vanfretti, & Chow, 2017), the authors propose a pseudo-dynamical hybrid model that can cope better with transient conditions that occur

frequently on hybrid grids with VSCs. The formulated converter model is based on a lossless power balance equation and the modulation index, which defines the relations between the voltage magnitude on the AC side and the DC side. More recent work (Ayiad, Leite, & Martins, 2020) uses the same approach but includes the converter losses, formulated as a 2nd-order polynomial, into the power balance.

All previously listed SEs make use of non-linear converter equations to describe the linkage between the AC and the DC state variables. This results in the need for a SE algorithm that uses an iterative procedure to find a solution. These iterative SEs are non-optimal and no unique solution can be guaranteed; (Abur & Exposito, 1997) shows that using current magnitude measurements together with power flow measurements can cause the network to be not uniquely observable. Furthermore, suitable initial conditions need to be chosen to ensure convergence. Another problem in using an iterative algorithm is the computation time. SEs that run coupled with real-time control applications should find the optimal solution within time windows ranging from a few hundred of ms to a few seconds. Therefore, computational efficiency is crucial.

3.2.2 Adaptive Kalman Filter

Microgrids are very often subjected to steps and fast state variations that violate the process model of recursive SE based on KF (see Appendix 5). Therefore, a correct assessment of the prediction error covariance matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}$ during these phenomena is crucial for the correctness of the KF. Various methods have been proposed in the literature to assess the process noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} (e.g. (Odelson, Rajamani, & Rawlings, 2006; Zanni, Sarri, Pignati, Cherkaoui, & Paolone, 2014; Noriega & Pasupathy, 1997; Myers & Tapley, 1976; Zanni et al., 2016)). The work deployed in HYPERRIDE uses the PECE, which is introduced in (Zanni et al., 2016). The PECE method only requires the setting of a single parameter and ensures the positive semi-definiteness of the estimated KF process covariance matrix (required to guarantee numerical stability). The method relies on the previous innovations as defined in (101) and computes an estimate of the prediction error covariance $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$ without first making an estimation of the process noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q}_k . The PECE method assumes the process model is an auto-regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) (0,1,0) model (Debs & Larson, 1970), the system is fully observable and the measurement model is linear, fully known and time-invariant. The measurement covariance matrix \mathbf{R} is assumed to be known. PECE considers that, when a step occurs, the KF state prediction (94) is inaccurate. Therefore, the absolute value of the innovations increases and the innovation covariance matrix approximation (1) changes. Consequently, the computed estimation covariance matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$ inflates and thus the Kalman gain too. Therefore, more weight will be put on the measurement model to instantly respond to the step change. To guarantee the positive definiteness of $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$, a constraint convex optimisation problem is solved (2).

The PECE is summarized here and all the details can be found in (Zanni et al., 2016) and (Zanni, 2017).

1. At time step k the a priori state estimate $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$ is computed together with the innovation $\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}_k \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$.
2. The covariance matrix of the innovations is given as:

$$\mathbf{S}_k = \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}_k \quad (1)$$

\mathbf{S}_k can be approximated by $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_k = \text{cov}(\mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{y}_{k-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{k-N+1})$, with N the number of considered past innovations. In the static conditions, the sample covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_k$ tends to converge to the true \mathbf{S}_k as N increases.

3. $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$ can now be estimated. Because solving (1) to $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$ will generally not produce a semi-definite matrix, a more adequate method has to be used: the authors of (Zanni et al., 2016) suggest solving the optimisation problem (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathcal{D}} \quad & \{-\log[\det(\mathcal{D})] + \text{trace}(\mathcal{D}\mathbf{E})\} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathcal{D} \text{ real symmetric, } \mathcal{D} \succ 0 \\ & \mathbf{I}_n - \mathcal{D} \succ 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with

$$\mathbf{R}_k^{-1/2} \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{V} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U} \\ \mathbf{0}_{m-n,n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \left(\mathbf{V}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_k^{-1/2} \hat{\mathbf{C}}_k \mathbf{R}_k^{-1/2} \mathbf{V}^{-T} \right)_{(1:n,1:n)} \quad (4)$$

4. The optimisation problem (2) is solved with YALMIP using the *sdpt3* solver. The estimation for the prediction covariance matrix can subsequently be computed as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k = (\mathbf{U}^{-1} (\mathcal{D}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}_n) \mathbf{U}^{-T}) \quad (5)$$

3.2.3 Transformer-like AC/DC Converter Model

A linear model of the converter is needed to link the AC phasors with the DC quantities. A transformer-like VSC model has been proposed in (Fratta & Scapino, 2004; Scapino, 2003). Figure 4 shows the model of one inverter leg. The transformer-like model is derived from the power balance equations and allows to model the lossless behaviour but also the conduction losses and the switching losses separately. The modelling of the losses requires few parameters that can be derived from the component's datasheet. (F. Scapino, 2005) further improved the transformer-like model accuracy by including the dead time and the high-impedance state. However, simulations show that the influence of these additional features is small and, therefore, they are not considered in this work.

Figure 4: Transformer-like model of an inverter leg of the AC/DC converter with RL filter.

The lossless two-port time-domain model of an inverter leg can be derived as shown in (6), in which $r(t)$ is defined as the leg binary switching function between '0' and '1'. This variable, averaged over its switching period, is the same as the modulating function that gives the voltage reference to the converter legs.

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_2(t) \\ i_1(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r(t) & 0 \\ 0 & -r(t) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_1(t) \\ i_2(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In the case of a lossy model, the conduction and switching losses can be included in the two-port model. The conduction losses account for the voltage drop over each conducting device. (Scapino, 2003) suggests considering these losses as a voltage source in series with the transformer's secondary side. The value of this voltage source depends on the direction of the alternating current and the switching function $s(t)$ that defines the conduction path. The **conduction loss** voltage drop in the time domain is represented by the difference between the ideal and the actual AC voltage (7) is analytically expressed as (8), in which V_T and V_D are the forward voltage drops over the transistor and the diode.

$$v_c(t) = V_{DC}r(t) - v_{AC} \quad (7)$$

$$v_c(t) = \text{sgn}(i_{AC}(t)) \left[\frac{V_T + V_D}{2} \right] + s(t) \frac{V_T - V_D}{2} \quad (8)$$

With $\text{sgn}()$ the sign function of the current in the time domain. The forward characteristics of the diode (referred to by subscript D) and transistor (referred to by subscript T) are approximated using a piecewise linear function with V_0 the forward voltage drop and R_0 the equivalent series resistance. Assuming the characteristics of the diode and the transistor hold, meaning $V_0 = V_{D0} = V_{T0}$ and $R_0 = R_{D0} = R_{T0}$, the conduction losses can be expressed as:

$$v_c(t) = V_0 \text{sgn}(i_{AC}(t)) + R_0 i_{AC}(t) \quad (9)$$

The **switching losses** are modelled as a current generator in parallel with the transformer's primary side. Different methods have been proposed to model these losses (Fratta & Scapino, 2004; Scapino, 2003; Fang et al., 2020, 2021). All methods are based on the transistor turn-on and turn-off losses (E_{ON} and E_{OFF}) under the test conditions:

$$E_{sw} = \frac{E_{ON} + E_{OFF}}{V_{test}I_{test}} I_{ac} V_{dc} \quad (10)$$

The equivalent time commutation constants characterising the transistor's turn-on and turn-off effects under the test conditions are defined as:

$$T_{ON} = \frac{E_{ON}}{V_{test}I_{test}}, \quad T_{OFF} = \frac{E_{OFF}}{V_{test}I_{test}} \quad (11)$$

The switching losses are to a first approximation, proportional to the DC voltage and the instantaneous AC current. (Fratta & Scapino, 2004) (Scapino, 2003) propose to model the current losses in the time domain for a fixed switching period as (12):

$$i_{s,IGBT}(t) = \frac{T_{ON} + T_{OFF}}{T_s} |i_{AC}(t)| \quad (12)$$

Other works, (Fang et al., 2021) and (Fang et al., 2020) propose to express the instantaneous energy losses due to the power semiconductor switching as (13):

$$E_{sw,IGBT} = (T_{ON} + T_{OFF}) V_{dc} \sqrt{2} I_{rms} \sin(2\pi f_{line} t), \quad (13)$$

where the current through the transistor is approximated as the fundamental line-frequency component of I_{ac} . Each time the transistor switches, some energy is lost. Averaged over one grid period, the total switching energy is defined as (14):

$$E_{sw,IGBT,T} = 2(T_{ON} + T_{OFF}) V_{dc} \sqrt{2} I_{rms} \sum_{n=1}^{N/2} \sin \frac{2\pi n}{N}, \quad (14)$$

with I_{rms} the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the current, $N = \frac{f_s}{f_{line}}$, f_s the switching frequency and f_{line} the line frequency. Using trigonometric identities, the energy losses in (14) can be reformulated as a current in parallel with the transformer primary side:

$$I_{sw,IGBT,T} = 2\sqrt{2} \frac{T_{ON} + T_{OFF}}{T_s} \frac{1}{N} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right) I_{rms}. \quad (15)$$

The switching current losses for the diode are modelled in a similar way using the time constant T_{REC} representing the reverse recovery at turn-off (16):

$$I_{sw,Diode,T} = 2\sqrt{2} \frac{T_{REC}}{T_s} \frac{1}{N} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right) I_{rms}. \quad (16)$$

The total switching current losses are defined as the sum of (15) and (16) .

3.3 Measurement Model

3.3.1 Converter Model

Lossless

Using the lossless transformer-like converter model Figure 4, the converter AC side can be linked with the DC side through the modulation index M . (17) describes the linkage for the lossless model, where $V_{ac} = V_2$ and $V_{dc} = V_1$ are the magnitudes of the AC and DC voltage.

$$V_2 = MV_1 \quad (17)$$

Because the AC system states are complex nodal voltages in Cartesian coordinates, (17) needs to be reformulated. By considering the modulation index as a complex variable $M = M_{re} + jM_{im}$, the problem can be reformulated so the DC quantities are linked with the AC phasors in a linear way:

$$V_{2,re} + jV_{2,im} = (M_{re} + jM_{im}) V_1 \quad (18)$$

Because it is interesting to infer V_1 as a function of the complex phasors, we define:

$$M_{re}^- = \frac{M_{re}}{M_{re}^2 + M_{im}^2}, \quad M_{im}^- = -\frac{M_{im}}{M_{re}^2 + M_{im}^2}, \quad (19)$$

which leads to:

$$V_1 + j0 = (V_{2,re}M_{re}^- - V_{2,im}M_{im}^-) + j(V_{2,re}M_{im}^- + V_{2,im}M_{re}^-) \quad (20)$$

This reformulation leads to two linear relations that link the DC quantities to the AC complex phasors:

$$V_1 = V_{2,re}M_{re}^- - V_{2,im}M_{im}^- \quad (21)$$

$$0 = V_{2,re}M_{im}^- + V_{2,im}M_{re}^- \quad (22)$$

The current at the DC side can be analogously related to the AC current phasor:

$$I_1 = -(I_{2,re}M_{re}^- - I_{2,im}M_{im}^-) \quad (23)$$

Lossy

In the case of a lossy converter, the loss terms, defined in (9) and (15), need to be expressed using the phasor representation.

The **conduction losses** consist of two terms: an ohmic voltage drop proportional to the current and a constant voltage drop that changes the sign depending on the current direction. The first term can straightforward be converted in phasor representation by taking the Fourier transform and only considering the fundamental frequency (24).

$$R_0 i_{AC}(t) \xrightarrow{\mathfrak{F}} R_0 I_{AC,re} + jR_0 I_{AC,im} \quad (24)$$

The second term is a square wave with amplitude V_0 . Using the Fourier expansion, the square wave can be represented by an infinite sum of sine waves. By neglecting the higher-order terms and taking the Fourier transform of the fundamental frequency, we can convert the time-domain expression into a phasor representation (25):

$$V_0 \operatorname{sgn}(i_{AC}(t)) \xrightarrow{\mathfrak{F}} V_0 \frac{4}{\pi} \cos(\theta_I) + jV_0 \frac{4}{\pi} \sin(\theta_I), \quad (25)$$

with θ_I the initial angle of the square wave function.

Using trigonometric identities, the voltage drop accounting for the conduction losses in an inverter leg can be written in phasor representation as:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{c,re} + jV_{c,im} &= (V_0 \frac{4}{\pi} \cos(\theta_I) + R_0 I_{ac,re}) + j(V_0 \frac{4}{\pi} \sin(\theta_I) + R_0 I_{ac,im}) \\ &= (V_0 \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{1}{|I_{AC}|} + R_0)(I_{ac,re} + jI_{ac,im}) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The current magnitude in the denominator is computed using the states of the previous time step. The introduced approximation is negligible due to: 1) New states are computed at a very high frequency (i.e. larger than 1 Hz) and in quasi-static conditions, little difference will be observed between two consecutive states. 2) In recursive SE, the process noise can account for this error¹. 3) The conduction voltage drop is at any time smaller than $0.005pu$. Therefore, even during large transients when the state would change abruptly between two consecutive time steps, the possible introduced error is very small. To represent the $V - I$ characteristic of the transistor with better accuracy, the real exponential relation can be used in preference to a linear piecewise function. Furthermore, the $R_{eq} - I$ characteristic, the ohmic resistance of the transistor as a function of its current can be derived from the semiconductor's datasheet. By using this characteristic, the value of the equivalent resistor R_{eq} is evaluated using the previously estimated state $|I_{ac}^{t-1}|$. Using R_{eq} , equation (26) is rewritten as (27).

$$V_{c,re} + jV_{c,im} = R_{eq}(|I_{ac}^{t-1}|) (I_{ac,re} + jI_{ac,im}). \quad (27)$$

The **switching losses** are also converted into Cartesian phasor representation. Both methods presented in Section II, (12) and (15) can be converted in a similar way by using the first-order Fourier expansion. It can be shown that both methods give the same numerical results.

¹The whiteness of this error is numerically proved in Section 3.5.2

$$I_{sw} = 2 \frac{T_{ON} + T_{OFF} + T_{REC}}{T_s} \frac{1}{N} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right) (\cos(\theta_I^{t-1}) I_{ac,re} + \sin(\theta_I^{t-1}) I_{ac,im}) \quad (28)$$

A **filter** at the AC side of the converter is required to reduce the harmonics to an acceptable level. Figure 4 shows the RL filter together with the lossy converter. The filter also needs to be included in the measurement model. We can write the voltage drop of the RL filter in phasor representation as:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{f,re} + jV_{f,im} &= (R_f + j\omega L_f)(I_{ac,re} + jI_{ac,im}) \\ &= (R_f I_{ac,re} - \omega L_f I_{ac,im}) + j(R_f I_{ac,im} + \omega L_f I_{ac,re}) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Integrating the transistor losses (27) (28) and the filter voltage drop (29) into the lossless expression derived in (21), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{DC} &= M_{re}^- (V_{g,r} + (R_f + R_{eq}) I_{ac,r} - \omega L_f I_{ac,i}) \\ &\quad - M_{im}^- (V_{g,i} + (R_f + R_{eq}) I_{ac,i} + \omega L_f I_{ac,r}) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

and

$$I_{DC} = - (I_{ac,re} M_{re}^- - I_{ac,im} M_{im}^-) + I_s, \quad (31)$$

with I_s as defined in (28). The exact values of the complex modulation index can easily be extracted from the VSC control and will be fed to the SE as a known variable.

Because the states of AC systems are often selected as the nodal voltages, the DC voltage and current in (30) and (31) need to be rewritten as a function of the nodal AC voltages instead of the current flows. We call the nodes of the AC branch connected to the VSC k and m , with m the node closest to the VSC. Using the expressions (32), (33) of the real and imaginary part of the current flow phasors at the branch between buses k and m , we can formulate the VSC lossy model representing the DC voltage as a function of the AC nodal voltage phasors.

$$I_{km,re} = g_{km,L}(V_{k,re} - V_{m,re}) - b_{km,L}(V_{k,im} - V_{m,im}) + g_{km,T}V_{k,re} - b_{km,T}V_{k,im} \quad (32)$$

$$I_{km,im} = g_{km,L}(V_{k,im} - V_{m,im}) + b_{km,L}(V_{k,re} - V_{m,re}) + g_{km,T}V_{k,im} + b_{km,T}V_{k,re} \quad (33)$$

with $g = g_{km}$ the conductivity and $b = b_{km}$ the susceptibility of the line km . Rewriting (30) using the current flow equations with $I_{ac,re} = I_{km,re}$ and $I_{ac,im} = I_{km,im}$ gives for the direct sequence equivalent (1-phase):

$$\begin{aligned} V_{DC} &= [M_{re}^- (1 + (R_f + R_{eq})(g^L + g^T) - \omega L_f(b^L + b^T)) \\ &\quad + M_{im}^- (\omega L_f(g^L + g^T) - (R_f + R_{eq})(b^L + b^T))] V_{m,re} \\ &\quad + [M_{re}^- (-(R_f + R_{eq})g^L + \omega L_f b^L) + M_{im}^- (-\omega L_f g^L + (R_f + R_{eq})b^L)] V_{k,re} \\ &\quad + [M_{re}^- ((R_f + R_{eq})(-b^L - b^T) - \omega L_f(g^L + g^T)) \\ &\quad + M_{im}^- (1 + \omega L_f(-b^L - b^T) - (R_f + R_{eq})(g^L + g^T))] V_{m,im} \\ &\quad + [M_{re}^- ((R_f + R_{eq})b^L + \omega L_f g^L) + M_{im}^- (\omega L_f b^L - (R_f + R_{eq})g^L)] V_{k,im}, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

The coefficients $C_{1..4}$ are introduced to simplify the above expression:

$$V_{DC} = C_1 V_{m,re} + C_2 V_{k,re} + C_3 V_{m,im} + C_4 V_{k,im}. \quad (35)$$

Unbalanced and 3-phase systems

In the case of an AC 3-ph system, the measurement matrix is extended to include all the a, b, c -phases of the considered states and measurements. Therefore, the equations (30) and (31) need to be adapted in order to incorporate the 3-ph phasors, because one DC quantity needs to be related to three complex phasors. Using Fortescue's transformation to decompose the 3-ph voltages and currents into their symmetrical components, an elegant and linear solution is obtained. The complex linear transformation is shown in (36), where $\alpha = e^{\frac{2}{3}\pi j}$ and $0, 1, 2$ represents respectively the zero, positive and negative component.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{0,re} + jV_{0,im} \\ V_{1,re} + jV_{1,im} \\ V_{2,re} + jV_{2,im} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & \alpha & \alpha^2 \\ 1 & \alpha^2 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} V_{a,re} + jV_{a,im} \\ V_{b,re} + jV_{b,im} \\ V_{c,re} + jV_{c,im} \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

Using the symmetrical components decomposition, (21) is reformulated as (37) where each sequence contributes to the DC voltage.

$$V_{DC} = M_{0,re}^- V_{0,re} + M_{1,re}^- V_{1,re} + M_{2,re}^- V_{2,re} - M_{0,im}^- V_{0,im} - M_{1,im}^- V_{1,im} - M_{2,im}^- V_{2,im} \quad (37)$$

By solving (36) and substituting the real and imaginary components of the sequences into (37), a linear relation is obtained that links the DC voltage to the three complex phasors in the abc-coordinate system.

For a 3-ph system, the complex modulation indices M^{abc} are transformed into their symmetrical components M^{012} using the Fortescue matrix (36). The variables C_i in (35) become vectors consisting of $[C_i^0 C_i^1 C_i^2]^T$, for $i \in [1 \dots 4]$. By re-transforming the variables into abc coordinates, the expression is obtained that links the DC voltage with the 3-ph AC phasors, this is directly used in the measurement model:

$$V_{DC} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re} \left((C_1^{012} + jC_3^{012})^T A^{-1} \right) \\ \text{Re} \left((C_2^{012} + jC_4^{012})^T A^{-1} \right) \\ \text{Im} \left(-(C_1^{012} + jC_3^{012})^T A^{-1} \right) \\ \text{Im} \left(-(C_2^{012} + jC_4^{012})^T A^{-1} \right) \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} V_{m,re}^{abc} \\ V_{k,re}^{abc} \\ V_{m,im}^{abc} \\ V_{k,im}^{abc} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

with A^{-1} the inverse of the Fortescue matrix. The terms in (38) correspond to the submatrices $[\mathbf{H}_{VSC-AC} \ \mathbf{H}_{VSC-DC}]$ in the hybrid AC/DC measurement model (46) that will be constructed in the next section.

When VSC only injects the positive sequence component, the terms M_0 and M_2 in (37) can be omitted and the model simplifies. Therefore, the terms C_i^{012} , for $i \in [1 \dots 4]$ in (38) only have a positive sequence term: $[0 \ C_i^1 \ 0]^T$ and thus the DC voltage will only influence the positive sequence of the AC voltage.

It is important to notice that the proposed linear model allows for representing the VSC independently of its control variables and parameters. Because the SE is formulated from the grid's perspective, the internal voltages and/or currents within the VSC are not considered. The VSC control scheme regulates the modulation index to track the preferred set points for $V_{dc} - Q_{ac}$, $P_{ac} - Q_{ac}$ or $V_{dc} - |V_{ac}|$. Therefore, the states are estimated regardless of the control variables and the parameters.

3.3.2 AC Network Model

Using PMUs for the data acquisition allows formulating the AC system in a fully linear way. The measurements vector consists of phase-to-ground nodal voltages, nodal current injections and current flows. In this work, the state variables, defined as the smallest set that fully describes the system, will be the nodal voltages for the AC network. The structure of the linear measurement model for the AC network is:

$$\mathbf{H}_{AC-AC} = [\mathbf{H}_V \quad \mathbf{H}_{I_{inj}} \quad \mathbf{H}_{I_{flow}}]^T \quad (39)$$

The construction of these sub-matrices is described in (Paolone et al., 2015).

3.3.3 DC Network Model

DMUs are responsible for the data acquisition in the DC network. The devices are time synchronised with the PMUs and have the same measurement frame rate. They provide nodal voltage, current injections and current flow measurements. Analog to the AC system, the expression of the current injections in node i connected to s nodes is:

$$I_i = \sum_{\ell=1}^s g_{i\ell} (V_i - V_\ell) \quad (40)$$

The expressions of the current flows at the branch between busses i and ℓ are:

$$I_{i\ell} = g_{i\ell} (V_i - V_\ell) \quad (41)$$

The structure of the measurement model for the DC network can be written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_{DC-DC} = [\mathbf{H}_V \quad \mathbf{H}_{I_{inj}} \quad \mathbf{H}_{I_{flow}}]^T \quad (42)$$

The sub-matrices are defined as:

$$\mathbf{H}_V = [\boldsymbol{\alpha}], \quad \text{where } \alpha_{i\ell} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = \ell \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq \ell \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{I_{inj}} = \mathbf{G}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{G} \text{ the conductivity matrix} \quad (44)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{I_{flow}} = [\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad \boldsymbol{\delta}], \quad \text{where } \begin{cases} \theta_{i\ell} = g_{i\ell} \\ \delta_{i\ell} = -g_{i\ell}, \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

with $g_{i\ell}$ the element at the i, ℓ position in the DC network's conductivity matrix.

3.4 Developed Linear State Estimation Model

3.4.1 Measurement model

The measurement model (46) is constructed using the submatrices of the VSC model (38), AC grid (39) and DC grid (42) defined in the previous section.

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{AC-AC} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{H}_{VSC-AC} & \mathbf{H}_{VSC-DC} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{H}_{DC-DC} \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

Depending on the grid topology, location of the measurement devices and the preference of DC state variables, we can choose to use the VSC voltage (30) or the VSC current (31) model for the measurement matrix. In case the DC states are the nodal voltages, we can link the voltage measurement at the DC side of the VSC to the state variables using a one-on-one relation. Therefore, the measured DC current can be related to the states using the current model (31). If the DC currents are the preferred states, similar reasoning is made.

Furthermore, the measurement model requires to satisfy several conditions to preserve linearity: 1) The AC measurements and states must be expressed in Cartesian coordinates, idem for the measurement noise (92). 2) The converter model requires the complex modulation index that is given as a known variable by the VSC. 3) To take the VSC losses into account, the current of the previous time step is evaluated to compute the equivalent ohmic resistance of the transistor and diode.

The measurement noise originates from two sources: the noise coming from sensors and the inaccuracies introduced in the phasor extraction at the PMU level. Table 1 shows the phase displacement and ratio error for several accuracy classes of the voltage transformers according to (*Instrument Transformers*; “*Additional requirements for electronic current transformers*,” 2011a). Table 2 summarizes the noise level for different percentages of magnitude and phase displacement of the rated current (*Instrument Transformers*; “*Additional requirements for electronic current transformers*,” 2011b). Because of the faster dynamic behaviour in micro-grids, P class PMUs are preferred that are characterized by a fast response. The typical maximum errors of P class devices with a total vector error of 0.14% are given in Table 3 (“IEEE Standard for Synchrophasor Measurements for Power Systems”, 2011b). Following the hypothesis for the summation of uncorrelated normal distributions, the cumulative maximum errors of the sensors and the PMUs are computed by summing the corresponding magnitude error and phase errors. The cumulative standard deviation of the measurement noise is equal to one-third of the maximum errors.

Table 1: Limits of ratio error and phase displacement of the voltage transformer.

IT class	ratio error (%)	phase displ. (mrad)
0.1	0.1	1.5
0.5	0.5	6
1	1	12

Table 2: Limits of ratio error and phase displacement of the current transformer for different values of the rated current.

IT class	ratio error (%)				phase displ. (mrad)				
	% of rated	5%	20%	100%	120%	5%	20%	100%	120%
0.1		0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	4.5	2.4	1.5	1.5
0.5		1.5	0.75	0.5	0.5	27	13.5	9	9
1		3.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	54	27	18	18

The PMU measurements are expressed in the Cartesian coordinate system. Therefore, the corresponding noise distributions in polar coordinates must also be transformed into rectangular coordinates as described in (Paolone et al., 2015). This coordinate transformation does not

Table 3: Limits of magnitude and phase error of the P class PMU and DMU.

Device	accuracy (%)	mag. error (%)	phase error (rad)
PMU (AC)	0.14	0.1	10^{-3}
DMU (DC)	0.14	0.1	-

preserve the normality of the noise distribution. However, for small noise levels, as sensors of classes 0.1 – 1, the effect is not noticeable and we can assume the noise in rectangular coordinates is normally distributed. The diagonal elements of the measurement noise matrix \mathbf{R} are composed of the aforementioned variances.

3.4.2 Adaptive Kalman Filter

The PECE method, introduced in (Zanni et al., 2016), relies on finding the solution of a determinant maximization (MAXDET) optimisation problem to infer the KF process noise covariance matrix. This problem, as given in (2), is time-consuming to solve and requires specific software. However, by considering the optimisation variable \mathcal{D} as a diagonal matrix, the problem can be significantly simplified to reduce the computation time. As the authors of (Zanni et al., 2016) described, the off-diagonal elements increase the response time and improve the state-tracking capabilities. However, even without considering these elements, the performance of the Adaptive Kalman Filter (AKF) is still significantly better than the original DKF during step responses. Assuming \mathcal{D} only has diagonal entries the MAXDET problem in (2) can be simplified to (47) by performing the mathematical transformations: 1) The logarithm of the determinant of a diagonal matrix can be rewritten as the sum of the logarithms of the individual diagonal elements. 2) The trace is reformulated as the inner product of the diagonal elements of the two matrices.

$$\min_{\mathcal{D}} \left\{ -\sum_{i=1}^n \log(\mathcal{D}_i) + \mathcal{D} \text{diag}(\mathbf{E})^T \right\}$$

$$s.t. \ 0 < \mathcal{D} \leq 1 \quad (47)$$

with \mathcal{D} a vector with as length the number of state variables. This is a simple optimisation problem that does not need any specific solver. This simplification hugely speeds up the problem so it can be used in a real-time application².

3.4.3 Bad Data Processing

After the estimation process, the presence of bad measurements is examined. Bad data that corrupts the measurements, originates from sensors (e.g. malfunctioning, biases and bad calibration) or telecommunication systems (e.g. noise and interference). The LNR test is used for the identification and elimination of these bad data. The test uses the measurement residuals (48) that are defined as the difference between the measurement and the reconstructed measurement computed using the state estimates (Van Cutsem, Ribbens-Pavella, & Mili, 1984) (Abur & Exposito, 2004).

²A numerical validation, presented in Section 3.5, showed that the diagonal approximation reduces the Central Processing Unit (CPU) time from 11.5 ± 0.26 s to 58.7 ± 2.8 ms.

$$r_i = z_i - \mathbf{H}_i \hat{x}_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (48)$$

Using (97), the residuals are reformulated and its covariance matrix can be computed (Zhang, Welch, Bishop, & Huang, 2013):

$$\begin{aligned} z - \mathbf{H}\hat{x} &= z - \mathbf{H}(\tilde{x} + \mathbf{K}(z - \mathbf{H}\tilde{x})) \\ &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K})(z - \mathbf{H}\tilde{x}) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cov}(z - \mathbf{H}\hat{x}) &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K}) \text{cov}(z - \mathbf{H}\tilde{x}) (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K}) \\ &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K}) \mathbf{S} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K}) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

with S the innovation covariance matrix as defined in (102). Using the definition of the Kalman gain (96), $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{K})$ can be rewritten as $\mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}^{-1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T} = \text{cov}(z - \mathbf{H}\hat{x}) &= (\mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}^{-1})\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}^{-1}) \\ &= \mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}^{-1}\mathbf{R} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Using (51), the normalised residuals are defined by (52), in which \mathbf{T}_{ii} represents the i^{th} diagonal element of the residual covariance matrix.

$$r_i^N = \frac{|r_i|}{\sqrt{\mathbf{T}_{ii}}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (52)$$

If $r_k^N > c$, with k the index of the LNR, this measurement will be suspected as bad data. c is the user-defined identification threshold, set at for instance 4. In case a measurement is identified as bad data, this measurement is eliminated and the KF re-estimates the states using the reduced measurement matrix. The above process is repeated until all normalised residuals are smaller than the defined threshold.

3.5 Numerical Validation

3.5.1 Network

The linear SE is validated in an EMTP-RV simulation of the CIGRE benchmark microgrid extended with a DC grid. Figure 5 shows the hybrid grid's topology with the loads and the power sources. The AC micro-grid has a base voltage of 400 V and the DC grid 800 V, the base power for both networks is 100 kW. Bus $B01$ is the *slack bus* that is connected to the 20 kV medium voltage grid through a transformer. The table in Figure 5 indicates the simulation's boundary conditions. In order to consider a more realistic model, a dynamic power injection profile coming from photovoltaic power generation has been added to the AC node $B09$ and the DC node $B23$. The PV generation profile is shown in Figure 6 and has been measured on the EPFL campus. The system unbalance is created by injecting a total difference of 20 kW between the phases. The VSC's control variables are the DC voltage and the reactive power at the AC side setpoints.

Figure 5: Hybrid AC/DC micro-grid with the connected sources and loads, the maximum power rating are indicated. The table defines the boundary conditions of the simulation.

Figure 6: Profile of the PV generation in nodes B09 and B23.

Measurements

The PMU and DMU locations are chosen to guarantee the observability of the system, i.e. the measurement model matrix \mathbf{H} is full rank. On Figure 5, the PMU locations are shown in red and the DMU locations are in blue. Table 4 summarizes the type of measurements that are provided for each bus.

The PMUs and DMUs provide measurements at 50 frames/s. The measurements are corrupted with white noise with a power spectral density identical to the noise of the PMU and the sensors used in the real system. The deployed current and voltage sensors for the AC and DC system have both an accuracy class of 0.5%. The measurement noise matrix is constructed using the corresponding sensors, PMU and DMU noise levels from Tables 1, 2 and 4 where the rated current of the sensors is chosen as the highest line ampacity in the network.

Table 4: PMU and DMU locations and measurement type in the Hybrid AC/DC microgrid.

Network	Measurement type	Bus #
AC	3-ph Nodal voltage, 3-ph Current injections	1,3,5,9,11,13,14
AC	3-ph Current flows	9-15,13-16,11-17,7-18
DC	Nodal voltage	19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26
DC	Current flows	19-23,20-24,21-25,22-26

States

The state vector is composed of the nodal AC voltage phasors in rectangular coordinates and the current flows in the DC network:

$$\mathbf{x} = \left[V_{1,re}^\ell, \dots, V_{k,re}^\ell, V_{1,im}^\ell, \dots, V_{k,im}^\ell, I_{ij}, \dots \right], \quad (53)$$

with ij the index of the DC current flows between buses [19 – 23, 20 – 24, 21 – 25, 22 – 26], ℓ the phases a, b, c and k the index of the AC-side nodal voltage phasors at the busses 1 to 18 except for bus 6 and 12. These two buses are zero-injection buses that are removed from the SE using the Kron Reduction as described in (Kettner, 2019). Reducing the number of non-injection nodes is required to satisfy the observability criteria. Because the current is chosen as the state for the DC system, the VSC voltage model (38) is used in the measurement model. For a 3-ph system, this results in 100 states and 120 measurements, meaning a redundancy factor of 1.2.

EMTP-RV time-domain simulation

The uncorrupted measurements and states of the network are obtained from an EMTP-RV time-domain simulation. The two-level converter is taken from the power electronics library and represents a detailed model of the power electronics switches and associated losses. The VSC is controlled using a control scheme that manages grid synchronisation under unbalanced conditions. In the simulation, the converters only inject the positive sequence currents. Therefore, correct detection of the voltage positive sequence components is essential. A double second-order generalized integrator (DGOSI) extracts the positive and negative sequence components of the grid voltage. The positive components are fed to a phase-locked loop (PLL) to extract the phase and the in-quadrature dq voltage components in the rotating synchronous reference frame. The active and reactive power references, converted to dq current references using the in-quadrature voltage components, are tracked using two coupled PI controllers with active saturation. The PI controllers are tuned using symmetrical optimum. A PWM signal at 5 kHz controls the switching of the Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT)s. The AC and DC power sources, representing the different loads and sources are implemented in the time domain using a controlled current source. The converter and power sources are characterised by transient start-up phenomena that are ignored in the SE.

The AC measurement are generated using a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) that calculates the phasor quantities of the instantaneous values of the current and voltage signals. The phasors are calculated over a sliding window of one grid period. Because the time step of the simulation is $1 \mu s$, 20000 samples are used to generate each phasor update. The measurements from the DMUs are generated similarly. However, instead of using a DFT to extract the phasor from the instantaneous signal, a moving average block has been used. The simulation model is made publicly available on the DESL GitHub page³.

The process model is the ARIMA (0,1,0) to satisfy the PECE hypotheses.

3.5.2 Numerical Validation of the Hybrid AC/DC State Estimator

The validation of the hybrid SE relies on testing the assumptions made in (99) for the prediction error and (100) for the estimation error. If these expressions hold, the expected distribution equals

³<https://github.com/DESL-EPFL>

the actual distribution and the hypothesis is valid. Therefore, the hybrid KF works properly and can be validated a posteriori (i.e. by means of the classical hypothesis verification process to assess the exactness of the SE model).

Validation of the estimation error

Figure 7 shows the actual and expected distribution of the estimation error. The latter equals the square root of the diagonal elements of the estimation error covariance matrix \hat{P} . The results are obtained for a 100 s dynamic time-domain simulation of 5000 observations with respect to a system state associated with the boundary conditions given by the table in Figure 5. We can notice that the fitted distributions are zero-biased and that their distributions are very similar to the expected distributions. Because of the readability of the figure, several AC state variables are omitted from the figure, however, these states exhibit the same behaviour. We can thus conclude that the hypothesis made in (100) is satisfied.

Figure 7: Actual and expected distribution of the estimation error for the DC states and several of the 3-phase AC states.

Validation of the prediction error

The actual and the expected prediction error distributions are shown in Figure 8. The expected distributions equal the square root of the diagonal elements of the prediction error covariance matrix. The fitted distribution has a zero mean and its distribution is very similar to the expected one. The states that are not shown for the readability of the figure, exhibit the same behaviour. The hypothesis made in (99) can thus be validated.

Figure 8: Actual and expected distribution of the prediction error for the DC states and several of the 3-phase AC states.

Measurement model validation

The correct modelling of the linear VSC model in (37) is demonstrated on the residuals. The residuals of the DC voltage measurements define the difference between the measured DC voltage and the DC voltage reconstructed using the AC state estimates and the measurement matrix. When the distribution of the V_{dc} residuals is zero-biased, the model is correct. Figure 9 shows the actual distribution of the residuals of the four DC voltages in busses $B19$ to $B22$, namely the busses connected to the VSC DC side. The mean value is added to illustrate the residuals are unbiased and thus can be concluded that the VSC model is correct. Furthermore, is the expected distribution, defined in (51) highlighted on histograms to show the correct assessment of the residual covariance matrix. This implicitly shows the correctness of the LNR test as we will discuss in the next section on bad data detection and identification.

The influence of the loss terms on the accuracy of the SE is illustrated in Figure 10. The norm of the estimation error is shown for the two SEs: one with a measurement model that includes the loss term, and one with a model that ignores the VSC losses. Indeed, the inclusion of the loss term reduces the estimation error and therefore increases the accuracy of the estimated states.

Figure 9: Actual and expected distribution of the residuals of the DC voltage measurements in nodes 18,19,20,21.

3.6 Experimental Validation

The SE with its unique linear measurement model illustrated in the previous section, has been validated on the real-life hybrid AC/DC microgrid at the EPFL. Since in a real experiment the true states are unobservable, the validation method introduced in the previous section cannot be used anymore. The validation is based on the analysis of the normalised residuals, i.e. the difference between the measurements and the reconstructed measurements computed using

Figure 10: Norm of the estimation error for the lossy and lossless VSC model. The latter does not account for the switching and conduction losses.

the estimated states $r = z - H\hat{x}$. Only when no bad data is present, this metric can be used to validate the measurement model. Intuitively, this can be explained as follows: when no bad data is present (i.e. the measurements are unbiased and the distributions are within the measurement noise), the measurement matrix is an exact mapping between the measurements and the estimated states. Therefore, if the difference between these two showcase a white statistical distribution, the measurement model is correct (this process is called the noise hypothesis verification). Figure 11 shows the distribution of the residuals for each measurement. The experiment has been conducted on September 14, 2022, in the afternoon during a quasi-steady-state operation of the network. The distribution is computed using 1000 state estimates captured over a 20 s horizon. As can be seen in Figure 11, the distributions of the normalised residuals of each measurement have zero-mean and standard deviations below 1, confirming the correctness of the estimated state of the experimental hybrid AC/DC grid.

Figure 11: Distribution of the residuals.

3.6.1 PECE Diagonal Approximation

Validation of the PECE diagonal method

The approximation of the PECE method is validated by verifying the estimation error distributions (100). Figure 12 shows the actual and the expected distributions of the PECE and the PECE diagonal approximation method. Both methods are initialised by fixing the process noise to 10^{-6} for N time steps. The first $2N$ time steps, accounting for N steps where the process noise is fixed and N time steps where the PECE is converging, are removed from the simulation

(Zanni et al., 2016). N is fixed at 2000 for both methods. The figure illustrates clearly the matching character of the distributions. The other state variables are omitted from the figure for readability, however, these states exhibit the same behaviour. We can thus conclude that the hypothesis is satisfied and the diagonal approximation is validated.

The dynamics of the DKF, the PECE and the PECE diagonal method are compared in Figure 13. After the initialisation time, a step in the injected power in node 7 is introduced and the response of the three methods is illustrated. The norm of the estimation errors clearly shows the large overshoot and the slow response of the DKF. PECE diagonal approximation has a larger overshoot than the PECE method but converges rapidly in less than 0.2 s.

Influence of parameter N

Figure 14 shows the influence on the norm of the estimation errors (left) and the CPU time (right) for different values of N , the number of elements in the approximation of the innovation covariance matrix. The error bars define the 10th and 90th percentile of the computational time. The normalised error is computed considering a 100 s simulation for different values of N . The computation time is averaged over the simulation that is run on an Apple Macbook Pro laptop (32GB memory, Quad-Core Intel i7 processor). The initialisation of the PECE method is the same as mentioned above. If N decreases, fewer samples are used in the estimation of the innovation covariance matrix and the measurement noise is less effectively filtered out. Therefore, the innovation covariance matrix is approximated less accurate and the norm of the estimation errors increases. Despite the lower accuracy, the dynamic response is faster for smaller N . This occurs because fewer samples are used and a step will have a larger influence on the innovation covariance matrix. The computational time slightly increases for increasing N , mainly because of the increasing complexity of the covariance matrix computation.

Figure 12: Actual and expected distributions of the estimation error of the PECE method and the PECE diagonal approximation method.

3.6.2 Bad Data Processing

The bad data identification and elimination capabilities of the LNR test are evaluated for the proposed SE. The LNR test identifies a measurement as erroneous when the normalised residual is larger than a predefined threshold. The optimal threshold, a compromise between the true positive and the true negative ratio is iteratively determined for the hybrid AC/DC grid. The True Positive Ratio (TPR) is the ratio of the successfully detected bad data point over the total number of bad data points, while the True Negative Ratio (TNR) is the same for the

Figure 13: Comparison of the dynamic response of the norm of the estimation errors between the DKF, PECE, and the PECE diagonal approximation method for $N = 500$.

Figure 14: Norm of the estimation errors and the corresponding computational time for different values of N in a 100s simulation.

non-erroneous measurement. Having two characteristics to evaluate the performance is crucial because a low threshold allows detecting many bad data points, but it could also misclassify correct measurements.

Erroneous measurements are systematically introduced in each of the measurement devices. 54 PMUs and 12 DMUs, defined in Table 4, measure the magnitude (and phase) of the AC and DC signals. For each measurement unit, a simulation is performed where several erroneous magnitude and phase measurements are introduced at random time steps. The erroneous measurement for measurement unit i at time step t is defined as $|z_i^t|(1 + \alpha)$ with α a positive or negative value (50 % probability) and as absolute value a randomly sampled value between $(c, 5c] * \sigma_i$. The value c is the predefined threshold and σ_i is the measurement noise. Each simulation is 300s and has 100 bad data points. Because of the transformation of the PMU measurements into rectangular coordinates, the erroneous measurement will propagate in both the real and imaginary parts. This will result in two coupled bad data points. The TPR and the TNR for bad data on the measurement magnitudes for a threshold of 4.5, are shown in Figure 15. This threshold is selected a posteriori. Since the value depends strongly on the system itself, an iterative process has been performed to find the threshold that exhibits the best bad data detection capabilities. The LNR test can successfully detect bad data in the large majority of the cases for both the AC and the DC systems. Furthermore, the TNR shows that only a small fraction of the good measurements are incorrectly identified as bad data given this threshold. The measurements of the current injections in node B_{01} have a low TPR between 52% and 85%. These measurements exhibit the following characteristics: the currents are large, $1.3pu$,

and the added noise is relatively small. Especially compared to the noise level of the states used to reconstruct this measurement. Therefore, the bad data, which is proportional to the noise level will also be small and thus hard to detect. Bad data detection for phasor angles (not shown here due to space limitations) exhibits the same characteristics. The TPR is between 0.4 and 1 and the TNR is between 0.99 and 1.

Figure 15: True negative rate and the true positive rate of the LNR test.

3.6.3 Comparison with Existing Methods

The proposed linear recursive SE is benchmarked against existing methods from the literature to assess its performance in terms of accuracy and computational time. A centralized non-linear WLS-based state estimation is used for the comparison (Xia et al., 2016). For the correctness of the assessment, the same simulation with the same voltage and current measurements is used as in the proposed SE.

The non-linear WLS is based on the widely adopted active power balance to relate the DC network to the AC network. The non-linear relation is included in the measurement model as a pseudo measurement, as defined in (54).

$$\mathbf{z}_{pseudo} = P_{AC}^{VSC} + P_{DC}^{VSC} + P_{loss}^{VSC} = 0, \quad (54)$$

The measurement vector is extended with the pseudo measurements as given in (55). The states \mathbf{x} are chosen as the real and imaginary part of the AC voltages and the DC voltage magnitude (56).

$$\mathbf{z} = [\mathbf{z}_{AC}, \mathbf{z}_{DC}, \mathbf{z}_{pseudo}] \quad (55)$$

$$\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{x}_{AC, re}, \mathbf{x}_{AC, im}, \mathbf{x}_{DC}] \quad (56)$$

Due to the nonlinearity of the active power balance, the linearized measurement model needs to be expressed using the partial derivatives of the active power balance with respect to the state variables (57):

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{AC, re} & \mathbf{H}_{AC, im} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{H}_{DC} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{pseudo}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_{AC, re}} & \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{pseudo}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_{AC, im}} & \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{pseudo}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_{DC}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (57)$$

The converter losses (58) are modelled similarly as in the proposed linear measurement model (27), following (F. Scapino , 2005).

$$P_{loss}^{VSC} = (V_{c,re} I_{km,re} + V_{c,im} I_{km,im}) + I_{sw} V_{dc}, \quad (58)$$

with V_c the voltage drop due to conduction losses and I_{sw} the switching current losses. The loss term P_{loss} is written as a function of the state variables as shown in (59):

$$\begin{aligned} P_{loss}^{VSC} = & (\Delta V_{re}^2 + \Delta V_{im}^2) (g_L^2 + b_L^2) (R_f + R_{eq}(|I_{ac}^{t-1}|)) \\ & + 2 \frac{T_{ON} + T_{OFF} + T_{REC}}{T_s} \frac{1}{N} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right) V_{dc} \cdot \\ & \left[\left(\cos(\theta_I^{t-1}) g_L + \sin(\theta_I^{t-1}) b_L \right) \Delta V_{re} \right. \\ & \left. + \left(-\cos(\theta_I^{t-1}) b_L + \sin(\theta_I^{t-1}) g_L \right) \Delta V_{im} \right], \quad (59) \end{aligned}$$

where the grid parameters are the same as introduced in (32) and $\Delta V_{re} = (V_{k,re} - V_{m,re})$ and $\Delta V_{im} = (V_{k,im} - V_{m,im})$.

The comparison is made using the time-domain simulation as introduced in Section V. The measurement noise of the voltage and current measurements is identical as for the KF. For the sake of simplicity, the noise level of the pseudo measurements is set at 10^{-6} , i.e. an extremely low value that does not make the measurement covariance matrix ill-conditioned. The non-linear WLS is solved using an iterative Newton-Raphson approach, with a tolerance of 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} . Table 16 summarizes the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the state estimates and the computational time for the proposed method and the non-linear WLS. It can be seen that the accuracy of the estimated states of the proposed recursive SE is almost one order of magnitude better than the WLS one, with a CPU utilization time that is 5 to 10 times better. On average, it takes the WLS SE 15.1 iterations to reach the required tolerance of 10^{-5} ; this explains the large improvement in computational time of the proposed SE.

The maximum estimation error at each time step is shown in Figure 16, where can be seen that the largest estimation error is a factor 10 smaller in the proposed method compared to the non-linear WLS.

Table 5: Accuracy and CPU time comparison between the DKF and the NL WLS.

	RMSE	CPU [ms]	Iterations
Non-linear WLS (10^{-6})	$1.812 \cdot 10^{-2}$	27.4 ± 5.6	47.2
Non-linear WLS (10^{-5})	$1.836 \cdot 10^{-2}$	12.2 ± 4.9	15.1
DKF (proposed method)	$1.386 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.86 ± 0.40	/

3.7 Conclusion

In this chapter, it is introduced a fully linear measurement model for the recursive SE of hybrid AC/DC micro-grids. The measurement model includes a lossy VSC model that is based on the decomposition of the modulation index into its real and imaginary parts. The complex modulation index can be directly obtained from the VSC controller. The model is further expanded for AC 3-ph unbalanced grids by using the symmetrical component decomposition. An EMTP-RV simulation of the CIGRE benchmark AC microgrid connected using 4 VSCs to an

Figure 16: Comparison of the maximum estimation error between the proposed DKF and the non-linear WLS SE.

8-node DC microgrid is used for testing the hybrid SE. The SE and the measurement model are validated numerically by verifying the hypotheses made on the prediction and the estimation error distributions, and experimentally by verifying the hypothesis of the measurement residuals. Furthermore, the influence of the lossy term of the VSC's model on the accuracy of the SE is illustrated. A comparison between the proposed SE and a non-linear WLS SE shows a major improvement in both CPU utilisation time and accuracy. The performance of the PECE diagonal approximation is shown and compared to the PECE method. The analysis has also shown that, for the considered AC/DC grid and estimation frame rate, the required CPU time makes it suitable for control applications. Finally, the ability of bad data detection and identification using the LNR test is verified for both AC and DC networks.

4 Optimal Power Flow of Hybrid AC/DC Grids

4.1 Introduction

Hybrid AC/DC OPF has been intensively studied in the application of HVDC (El-Marsafawy & Mathur, 1980) (Yang, Zhong, Bose, Xia, & Kang, 2017) (Hotz & Utschick, 2019). However, for AC/DC microgrids with multiple VSCs, less rigorous solutions have been proposed (Eghtedarpour & Farjah, 2014b) (Qachchachi, Mahmoudi, & El Hasnaoui, 2014) (Hosseinzadeh & Salmasi, 2015). This section first introduces the generic OPF problem with the power flow equations of the AC system, DC system and interface. Different OPF problem-formulating techniques are then discussed. The section ends with an overview and a general conclusion.

4.1.1 The Optimal Power Flow Problem

The generic OPF problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{opt.variables} && \text{cost function} \\
 & \text{s.t.} && \text{grid constraints} \\
 & && \text{operational constraints,}
 \end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

where: 1) The cost function expresses the grid operational cost, in which the provision of ancillary services or primary and/or secondary support of the higher-voltage grid can also be included. The cost function might include a penalty for constraint violation (i.e. the so-called "soft constraints"). 2) The constraints take into account the limitations of the grid currents and voltages via their coupling with Kirchhoff's laws, and the limitations of the resources connected to the grid. 3) The decision variables are the controllable resources' set points (e.g. P/Q of the grid following resources or V/F of grid forming ones) (Paolone & Le Boudec, 2019).

4.1.2 Grid and Operational Constraints

Consider a generic hybrid AC/DC network consisting of \mathcal{K}_{ac} AC nodes, χ_{AC} AC lines, \mathcal{K}_{dc} DC nodes and χ_{DC} DC lines.

AC network model The non-approximated branch power flows for each line $(i, j) \in \chi_{AC}$ are written as (the symbols are introduced in section 3.3):

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{ij}^{ac} &= g_{ij} (v_i^2 - v_i v_j \cos(\theta_{ij})) - b_{ij} v_i v_j \sin(\theta_{ij}) \\
 Q_{ij}^{ac} &= -b_{ij} (v_i^2 - v_i v_j \cos(\theta_{ij})) - g_{ij} v_i v_j \sin(\theta_{ij})
 \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

The nodal power balance in each node $i \in \mathcal{K}_{AC}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_i^{ac} &= \sum_{(i,j) \in \chi_{AC}} P_{ij}^{ac} + \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_{AC}} G_{ij} \right) v_i^2 \\
 Q_i^{ac} &= \sum_{(i,j) \in \chi_{AC}} Q_{ij}^{ac} + \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_{AC}} -B_{ij} \right) v_i^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

The voltage and current flow limits are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{V} &\leq V \leq \overline{V} \\ I &\leq \overline{I} \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

And the operational limits of the generators can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{P} &\leq P \leq \overline{P} \\ \underline{Q} &\leq Q \leq \overline{Q}, \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

where \underline{X} and \overline{X} indicate the lower and upper limits.

DC network model

For the DC grid, the equations are very similar. The branch power flow for each branch $(i, j) \in \chi_{DC}$ are given as:

$$P_{ij}^{dc} = g_{ij} (v_i^2 - v_i v_j) \quad (65)$$

The nodal power balance in each node $i \in \mathcal{K}_{DC}$:

$$P_i^{dc} = \sum_{(i,j) \in \chi_{DC}} P_{ij}^{dc} \quad (66)$$

The voltage limits, current limits, as well as generation capacity limits, are identical as in the AC system.

VSC model

The VSC, at the interface between the AC and DC grid, is often modelled using the active power balance:

$$P^{ac} + P^{dc} + P^{loss} = 0 \quad (67)$$

Different methods have been used to model the converter losses: (Hotz & Utschick, 2019) (Ahmed, Eltantawy, & Salama, 2017) approximate the losses term P^{loss} by a loss term β proportional to the active power. (Mešanović, Muenz, & Ebenbauer, 2018) models the loss term using a resistance on the AC and on the DC side. Other works (Yang et al., 2017) (Bahrami, Therrien, Wong, & Jatskevich, 2016) make a more accurate approximation by considering the losses as a quadratic term in the form:

$$P^{loss} = a + b|I| + c|I|^2, \quad (68)$$

where a, b, c are positive coefficients. a represents the no-load loss, b accounts for the linear losses (e.g. switching losses) and the quadratic term accounts typically for the conduction losses.

The works (Yang et al., 2017) (Bahrami et al., 2016) include the VSC capacity constraint as a current limitation: $|I| \leq \overline{I}$, which is transformed into an apparent power constraint. (Bahrami et al., 2016) further improves the VSC model by adding a limitation on the reactive power output and upper bounds of the AC voltage magnitude by using the maximal modulation factor. Reference (Wu, Zhao, & Zhang, 2021) approximates the VSC by a reactive power source and a resistor. However, this only allows modeling the reactive compensation capability of the converter. Other works simply consider the converter as an ideal device and ignore the losses (Hosseinzadeh & Salmasi, 2015) (Qachchachi et al., 2014).

4.1.3 OPF Problem Formulation Techniques

The grid and operational constraints defined in 4.1.2 are not necessarily convex. The non-convex nature arises from the power flow equations and the inclusion of the quadratic models (e.g. used to express the VSC losses). Due to this, it is hard to determine the global minimum of OPF problems. Additionally, if the OPF runs in real-time for an intra-day control, a fast and accurate computation is required. A large number of techniques have been formulated to solve this problem. Generally, we can differentiate two approaches that are used to simplify the problem: 1) From the modelling perspective and 2) by relaxation of the non-linear and non-convex constraints.

Simplification from the modelling perspective

In the first approach, the physics of the problem is reformulated by e.g. linearizing the equation around a certain point (e.g. given by the SE). This approach reduces the accuracy of the solution, but because of the linearization, the problem can be solved in an efficient and computationally inexpensive way. This method is associated with the concept of sensitivity coefficients i.e. the partial derivatives of a voltage with respect to the control variables. The authors of (Gupta, Sossan, & Paolone, 2019) use SCs of the voltage, current and losses to develop a linear model for AC grids. They demonstrate that, when the Sensitivity Coefficients (SC)s are updated dynamically, the linearized model has a superior performance in terms of computational speed and accuracy of the grid constraints compared to the exact power flow model. In the application of hybrid AC/DC grids, reference (El-Marsafawy & Mathur, 1980) uses the SCs of the AC grid, DC grid and the VSC model to model the grid constraints. However, they consider a thyristor-based VSC model. For IGBT-based VSC, reference (Yang et al., 2017) proposes an approximation of the quadratic VSC loss constraint (68) using a first-order Taylor expansion.

Simplification by constraints relaxation

Most works on hybrid AC/DC OPF transform the non-convex and non-linear constraints by suitably defined relaxations. This approach adds new equations in order to change the solution space to convexify it. The added constraints can be more strict (inner relaxation), and thus compress the solution set, or less strict, (namely outer relaxation), when they enlarge the solution space outside the feasible one. The latter, however, can create complications because optimal operating points can be identified outside the feasible solution set.

In the application of hybrid AC/DC grids, several relaxation techniques have been proposed: (Wu et al., 2021) (Bahrami et al., 2016) propose a semi-definite relaxation and demonstrate the relaxation to be exact by showing that the ignored rank constraint is satisfied under 'mild' technical conditions. In (Baradar, Hesamzadeh, & Ghandhari, 2013) (J. Li, Liu, Wang, Low, & Mei, 2018) (Mešanović et al., 2018), the authors used a second-order cone (SOC) relaxation to transform the quadratic constraints into conic constraints. This SOC program is convex and can be solved efficiently (Lobo, Vandenberghe, Boyd, & Lebret, 1998). However, one of the main drawbacks of these solutions is the high computation time, which can make this approach less interesting for real-time applications. Because of the unbalanced nature of AC microgrids, 3-ph OPF problems are explored that take unbalances into account and can exploit the active and reactive power injections in each phase individually (Bruno, Lamonaca, Rotondo, Stecchi, & La Scala, 2011).

The section is structured as follows: Section 4.1 presents the problem and possible solutions of

the unified OPF hybrid AC/DC networks. Section 4.2 presents a novel method used to compute the sensitivity coefficient of hybrid networks analytically. In Section 4.4, the OPF algorithm is validated in the EMTP-RV simulation environment and a numerical example is presented to demonstrate the use of the SC to represent the grid constraints in an OPF control. The conclusions are given in Section 4.5.

4.2 Developed Methodology

This section develops an extension to the voltage sensitivity coefficients for hybrid AC/DC networks. The linearization technique is solely dependent on the grid's topology and state, which is provided with every 20 ms from the real-time SE presented in Chapter 3. Because of the fast state updates, this method can represent the grid constraints very accurately.

The current control loop of the VSC intrinsically decouples the d- and q-axis. This allows both axes to be controlled individually and, therefore, two variables can be controlled simultaneously (Chai, Zhang, Dou, Hao, & Zheng, 2016): e.g. $P_{ac} - |V_{ac}|$ control leads to a typical PV node, $P_{ac} - Q_{ac}$ leads to a typical PQ node that allows us to use the traditional power flow theory. However, at least 1 VSC is required to control the DC voltage (V_{dc}) to guarantee a stable voltage at the DC network (Baradar, Ghandhari, & Van Hertem, 2011). We call the DC node connected to this VSC the 'DC slack'. The DC voltage control can be combined with the control of Q_{ac} or $|V_{ac}|$. This control scheme, however, does not allow to use the traditional theory of PV and PQ nodes anymore and an extension of the theory is needed. A summary of the different control modes of a VSC in hybrid AC/DC systems is shown in Table 6, based on (Chai et al., 2016). The formulation of the problem is dependent on the controlled VSC parameters. The most common pair of control variables are: $V_{dc} - Q_{ac}$, $P_{ac} - Q_{ac}$, $V_{dc} - |V_{ac}|$. Note that if a dominating resource is connected to the DC network with a sufficient capacity and power rating, this resource could also be used to control the DC voltage and all the VSC interfacing nodes can be considered as PQ and/or PV nodes. However, since the DC energy resources are distributed and typically have a similar power rating, one of the VSCs is required to serve as 'DC slack'.

Table 6: Control modes of a VSC in hybrid AC/DC grids.

Node type	d-axis control	q-axis control
PQ node	constant P_{ac}	constant Q_{ac}
PV node	constant P_{ac}	constant $ V_{ac} $
'DC slack' type Q_{ac}	constant V_{dc}	constant Q_{ac}
'DC slack' type $ V_{ac} $	constant V_{dc}	constant $ V_{ac} $

4.2.1 Load Flow in Hybrid AC/DC Networks

A generic schematic of the hybrid AC/DC network is shown in Figure 17. As already introduced, the network consists of $n \in \mathcal{K}_{ac}$ AC nodes and $m \in \mathcal{K}_{dc}$ DC nodes. Five different type of nodes are present in the network Table 7: *Slack* $\in \mathcal{M}_{Slack}$, *PQ node* $\in \mathcal{M}_{PQac}$, *VSC_{ac} node* $\in \mathcal{M}_{VSCac}$, *VSC_{dc} node* $\in \mathcal{M}_{VSCdc}$ and a *P node* $\in \mathcal{M}_{PQdc}$ in the DC grid. Note that Figure 17 only contains one VSC, however, the developed theory is valid for multiple VSCs that have different control schematics. In what follows, the power flow equations for each type of node are presented.

Figure 17: Schematic of a generic hybrid AC/DC network interlinked by VSCs.

Table 7: Different types of nodes in hybrid AC/DC networks with their control variables.

Node type	Imposed/ Control param. \mathcal{X}	Param. to be determined
Slack	$ E /\angle E$	P, Q
PQ ac	P, Q	$ E /\angle E$
VSC ac	Q	$P, E /\angle E$
VSC dc	$ E $	P
PQ dc	P	$ E $

Slack node

The voltage magnitude is fixed at 1 p.u. and its argument is fixed to be 0 (phase angle of the reference node). When multiple slack nodes are present in the AC and or DC network, the power share of each slack has to be taken into account.

$$\operatorname{Re}\{E_i\} = E_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{Slack} \quad (69)$$

$$\operatorname{Im}\{E_i\} = 0, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{Slack} \quad (70)$$

PQac node

The AC nodes that are not connected to a VSC, are PQ nodes.

$$\operatorname{Re}\left\{E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n\right\} = P_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{PQac} \quad (71)$$

$$\operatorname{Im}\left\{E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n\right\} = Q_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{PQac} \quad (72)$$

VSCac node

The control of the VSC is typically programmed such that the reactive power setpoint equals the injected power after the filter. Therefore, the filter should not be included in (73). The converter reactive power losses, however, are not taken into account in the converter's control loops and are represented by loss term.

$$\operatorname{Im}\left\{E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n\right\} - \operatorname{Im}\{S_{loss}\} = Q_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{VSCac} \quad (73)$$

VSCdc node

The active power balance is used to relate the converter's DC side to the AC side. The converter

losses and the active power loss over the filter have to be accounted for.

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_f \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} = \\ & E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{M}_{VSCac}, j \in \mathcal{N}_{VSCdc} \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

When the AC system is interfaced with the DC system in more than one node, the above equations are still valid.

P(Q)dc node

The DC nodes that are not connected to a VSC are P(Q) nodes. Because the reactive power is zero, we can still apply the traditional theory for AC systems.

$$E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m = P_j, \quad \text{for } j \in \mathcal{N}_{PQdc} \quad (75)$$

4.2.2 Sensitivity Coefficients for Hybrid Networks

The voltage sensitivity coefficients with respect to \mathcal{X} that need to be determined are:

$$\frac{\partial |E_{PQac}|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \frac{\partial \angle E_{PQac}}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \frac{\partial |E_{VSCac}|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \frac{\partial \angle E_{VSCac}}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \frac{\partial E_{PQdc}}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \quad (76)$$

- where, \mathcal{X} equals to: $P_{ac}, Q_{ac}, Q_{vsc}, V_{dc}, P_{dc}$.
- Since the slack node and the VSC dc node imposes the voltage magnitude and/or angle, the partial derivative of this voltage with respect to any control parameter \mathcal{X} except for itself is 0.
- The partial derivative of any voltage with respect to itself is 1.

By computing the partial deviates of the equations (70) to (75) with respect to \mathcal{X} , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Re}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{1}{|E_i|} \frac{\partial |E_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{|E_n|} \frac{\partial |E_n|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] - \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Im}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{\partial \angle E_i}{\partial \mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial \angle E_n}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] = \frac{\partial |P_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{N}_{PQac} \\ & \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Im}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{1}{|E_i|} \frac{\partial |E_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{|E_n|} \frac{\partial |E_n|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Re}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{\partial \angle E_i}{\partial \mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial \angle E_n}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] = \frac{\partial |Q_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{N}_{PQac} \\ & \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Re}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{1}{|E_i|} \frac{\partial |E_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{|E_n|} \frac{\partial |E_n|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] - \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Im}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{\partial \angle E_i}{\partial \mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial \angle E_n}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] + \operatorname{Re}\left\{ \frac{\partial S_f}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right\} + \operatorname{Re}\left\{ \frac{\partial S_{loss}}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right\} = \\ & \quad \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} F_{k,m} \left[\frac{1}{E_k} \frac{\partial E_k}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{E_m} \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right], \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{N}_{VSCac}, k \in \mathcal{M}_{VSCdc} \\ & \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Im}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{1}{|E_i|} \frac{\partial |E_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{|E_n|} \frac{\partial |E_n|}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \operatorname{Re}\{F_{i,n}\} \left[\frac{\partial \angle E_i}{\partial \mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial \angle E_n}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] - \operatorname{Im}\left\{ \frac{\partial S_{loss}}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right\} = \\ & \quad \frac{\partial |Q_i|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \quad \text{for } i \in \mathcal{N}_{VSCac} \\ & \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} F_{k,m} \left[\frac{1}{E_k} \frac{\partial E_k}{\partial \mathcal{X}} + \frac{1}{E_m} \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial \mathcal{X}} \right] = \frac{\partial |P_k|}{\partial \mathcal{X}}, \quad \text{for } k \in \mathcal{M}_{PQdc} \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

The five equations in (77), one for each node type, are linear in terms of the partial derivatives defined in (76) and are only a function of the grid's state, topology, lines parameters and VSC

filters parameters. The linear set of equations can be written in matrix form (78) where the coefficient A_i and b_i correspond to the linear terms in (77). Recall that the states are computed every 20 ms by the linear and exact SE presented in chapter 3. Dependent on the node type, \mathcal{X} represents the voltage or power injection (see table 7). The A matrix is identical for each node, while the b matrix changes for each node. Matrix A can thus be computed once for the full network to decrease the computational time even further.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & A_{14} & A_{15} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} & A_{24} & A_{25} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} & A_{34} & A_{35} \\ A_{41} & A_{42} & A_{43} & A_{44} & A_{45} \\ A_{51} & A_{52} & A_{53} & A_{54} & A_{55} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \partial|E_{PQac}|/\partial\mathcal{X} \\ \partial\angle E_{PQac}/\partial\mathcal{X} \\ \partial|E_{VSCac}|/\partial\mathcal{X} \\ \partial\angle E_{VSCac}/\partial\mathcal{X} \\ \partial E_{PQdc}/\partial\mathcal{X} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ b_4 \\ b_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (78)$$

Once the SC are computed, they are easily used in the optimisation problem to represent the grid constraints.

4.2.3 Current Sensitivity Coefficients

Using the admittance matrix, the nodal current injections can be related to the nodal voltages that are derived from the previous analysis:

$$I_{ij} = Y_{ij}(E_i - E_j) \quad (79)$$

Therefore, the current injection sensitivity coefficients are written as:

$$\frac{\partial\angle I_{ij}}{\partial\mathcal{X}} = Y_{ij}^{ac} \left(\frac{\partial\angle E_i}{\partial\mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial\angle E_j}{\partial\mathcal{X}} \right) \quad (80)$$

$$\frac{\partial\angle I_{km}}{\partial\mathcal{X}} = Y_{km}^{dc} \left(\frac{\partial\angle E_k}{\partial\mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial\angle E_m}{\partial\mathcal{X}} \right) \quad (81)$$

The branch current flows are defined as:

$$\frac{\partial\angle I_{ij}}{\partial\mathcal{X}} = Y_{ij}^{ac} \left(\frac{\partial\angle E_i}{\partial\mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial\angle E_j}{\partial\mathcal{X}} \right) \quad (82)$$

$$\frac{\partial\angle I_{km}}{\partial\mathcal{X}} = Y_{km}^{dc} \left(\frac{\partial\angle E_k}{\partial\mathcal{X}} - \frac{\partial\angle E_m}{\partial\mathcal{X}} \right) \quad (83)$$

The current SCs are directly included in the optimisation problem to limit the grids' ampacity constraints.

4.3 Generalization

Depending on the controlled parameters of the VSC, different systems of equations can be written to model the system's behaviour. In case multiple VSCs are present with different controlled parameters, the below equations are combined.

control parameters: $V_{dc} - Q_{ac}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= P_i \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= Q_i \\
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_f \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} - \operatorname{Im} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= Q_i \\
 E_k \sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{k,m}^{dc} E_m &= P_k
 \end{aligned}$$

control parameters: $P_{ac} - Q_{ac}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= P_i \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= Q_i \\
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_l \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{l,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= P_l \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_l \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{l,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} - \operatorname{Im} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= Q_l \\
 E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_f \right\} - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= P_l \\
 E_k \sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{k,m}^{dc} E_m &= P_k
 \end{aligned}$$

control parameters: $V_{dc} - |V_{ac}|$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= P_i \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= Q_i \\
 |E_l| &= E_l \\
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_l \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{l,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_f \right\} + \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m \\
 E_k \sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{k,m}^{dc} E_m &= P_k
 \end{aligned}$$

control parameters: $P_{ac} - |V_{ac}|$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= P_i \\
 \operatorname{Im} \left\{ E_i \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{i,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} &= Q_i \\
 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ E_l \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{l,n}^{ac} E_n \right\} - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= P_l \\
 |E_l| &= E_l \\
 E_j \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} Y_{j,m}^{dc} E_m - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_f \right\} - \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{loss} \right\} &= P_l \\
 E_k \sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} Y_{k,m}^{dc} E_m &= P_k
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4 Numerical Validation

4.4.1 Network

The analytical method to compute the SC is next validated numerically and its application is demonstrated in an OPF problem. The topology of the hybrid network is the same as introduced in Section 2 and the boundary condition is defined in Figure 5. The hybrid network is modelled in EMTP-RV and has an AC base voltage of 400 V and a DC voltage of 750 V, the base power for both networks is 100 kW. Bus $B01$ is the *slack bus* that is connected to the 20 kV medium voltage grid through a transformer.

4.4.2 Validation of the Analytically Computed Sensitivity Coefficients

The EMTP-RV steady-state simulation is used as the initial point for the validation of the proposed analytical method. Each control variable's \mathcal{X} setpoint has been changed by 10 % to create a small perturbation. The perturbed variables are the active and reactive power for the PQ nodes and Q_{ac}, V_{dc} for the nodes connected to the resp. AC and DC side of the AFEs. The numerical voltage sensitivity coefficient with respect to \mathcal{X} are computed as follows:

$$K_{\mathcal{X}} = \frac{V_i^{t0} - V_i^{t1}}{\mathcal{X}_i^{t0} - \mathcal{X}_i^{t1}} \quad (84)$$

These coefficients are compared with the analytically computed SC as described in the previous section. The results are shown in figures 18, 19, 20 for a perturbation for control variable E22 (DC voltage), P23 (DC power) and Q18 (reactive power setpoint of the AFE). The figures show in red the ground truth i.e. based on the perturbation in the EMTP-RV simulation and the blue dots indicate the voltage sensitivity coefficients for the 3 phases in each node computed using the proposed analytical method. We can see that both graphs are matching and therefore the analytical method can be validated.

4.4.3 Numerical Example

To demonstrate the use of the sensitivity coefficients for hybrid networks, a simple optimal power flow control is presented. Two objectives are compared: 1) Voltage control, where the

Figure 18: The real and imaginary part of the voltage sensitivity coefficients with respect to the controllable DC voltage in Node B22. Red indicates the ground truth, and blue the analytically computed.

Figure 19: The real and imaginary part of the voltage sensitivity coefficients with respect to the controllable reactive power injection of the AFE in Node B18. Red indicates the ground truth, and blue the analytically computed.

Figure 20: The real and imaginary part of the voltage sensitivity coefficients with respect to the controllable DC power in Node B23. Red indicates the ground truth, and blue the analytically computed.

voltage deviation is minimized and 2) Where the self-consumption is maximized i.e. the power interchange with the upper layer medium-voltage grid is minimised. Optimisation problem 1 is

written as (85) and problem 2 as (86)

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Delta P_{AC}, \Delta Q_{AC}, \Delta P_{DC}, \Delta V_{DC}} \quad & \|E_{ref}^t - E_i^t\| \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (87), (88), (89) \text{ and } (90) \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Delta P_{AC}, \Delta Q_{AC}, \Delta P_{DC}, \Delta V_{DC}} \quad & |P_{slack}^t| \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (87), (88), (89) \text{ and } (90) \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

Where the constraints are defined as follows:

The linearized expressions that links the nodal voltage in each bus to the control variables is written as (87).

$$\Delta|E_i| = \mathbf{K}_P^V \Delta \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{K}_Q^V \Delta \mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{K}_V^V \Delta |\mathbf{V}| \quad (87)$$

where \mathbf{K}^V is the vector of voltage sensitivity coefficients with respect to the active power, reactive power and DC voltage of the controllable DERs. The SC are analytically computed using the proposed method.

The operational points of each DER i are constraint by:

$$0 < P_i < \overline{P}_i \quad (88)$$

$$\underline{Q}_i < Q_i < \overline{Q}_i \quad (89)$$

And current flows are constraint by the line ampacity limits:

$$|I_{ij}| < |\overline{I}_{ij}|, \quad (90)$$

where

$$\Delta|I_{ij}| = \mathbf{K}_P^I \Delta \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{K}_Q^I \Delta \mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{K}_V^I \Delta |\mathbf{V}| \quad (91)$$

\mathbf{K}^I is the vector of current SCs with respect to the active power, reactive power and DC voltage of the controllable DERs (defined in (82), (83)). The limits of the interfacing converters can be included together with an additional constraint to avoid no-load operation. Note that this is a trivial optimisation problem that solely serves to demonstrate the use of the SC. The SC can be used to model the grid constraints in any OPF problem regardless of the objective function.

A numerical simulation is performed using the hybrid microgrids topology presented in Figure 5. Realistic generation and load profiles are used that are measured at the EPFL campus. Node 14 hosts an EV charging station, nodes 3, 13, 23 and 25 are connected to a residential load and in nodes 9, 11, 24 and 26 a PV unit is connected. Only nodes 9 and 26 have controllable PV units. Table 8 summarises the controllability of the resources and the nodes these are connected to.

The power profiles of all the distributed resources are shown in Figure 21. The optimisation horizon is 24 hours with a time step of 5 minutes.

The control results are presented in Figure 22 and 23. Figure 22 shows the power injection of the two controllable PV busses for both optimisation problems. The MPP profile is highlighted in the grey area. Figure 23 shows the voltage distribution of each node of the hybrid network over the 24h optimisation horizon. For the first control problem, the voltage control, we can see that the controllable PV units are curtailed more in order to keep the voltage distribution over the optimisation horizon smaller.

Table 8: Boundary conditions of the OPF problem

Node type	Nodes	Resource type
Controllable resources	B09, B26	PV
	B19, B20, B21, B22	V_{dc} of AC/DC AFE
Uncontrollable resources	B14	EV
	B11, B24	PV
	B03, B13, B23, B25	Residential load

Figure 21: Power profiles in the non-zero injection nodes. The PV profiles are the MPP. The controllable resources are indicated in the dashed line.

Figure 22: MPP and PV generation profiles for the voltage control and maximisation of the self-consumption. The top figure shows the PV profiles for node B09, the bottom figure for node B26.

4.5 Conclusion

In this section, it is introduced an exact linearized load flow model to describe the constraints of hybrid AC/DC microgrids. The proposed model includes the converter and filter losses.

Figure 23: Voltage distribution for the voltage control and the maximisation of self-consumption.

Furthermore, an analytical method is presented to use the above-mentioned linearized load flow equations to compute the voltage sensitivity coefficients; i.e. the partial derivative of the voltage with respect to any control variable (e.g. P_{AC} , Q_{AC} , P_{DC} , V_{DC}). These coefficients are used to model the grid constraints in a linear way in an OPF problem. The section presents a numerical validation of the proposed method by comparing the analytically computed SCs with those obtained from an EMTP-RV simulation. Finally, a numerical example is presented where an optimal control problem is constructed for the hybrid AC/DC grid at the EPFL.

5 Conclusions

This document presented the technical novelties and the achievements of the HYPERRIDE Task 6.1. The report gives an in-depth update on the technological advancements of the hybrid AC/DC network developed at the EPFL. The developed electrical network architecture as well as the installed DER and AFEs are described. The 18-node AC network is interfaced with the 8-node DC network using 4 AFEs. The network contains multiple resources such as PV units, BESS, supercapacitor storage, a load emulator and an EV charging station. Each resource is interfaced with a recourse agent, which is responsible to translate the setpoints given by the centralised control to each unique communication protocol. PMUs and DMUs measure synchronised voltage and current phasors to provide real-time state estimation with time-aligned measurements.

The report has illustrated the development of a real-time SE is based on an exact linear measurement model to relate the measurements with the system state. The AC/DC interface is included in the measurement model by relying on the complex modulation index, which is directly provided by the AFE controller. The most likelihood state is estimated in a recursive estate estimator process based on a DKF. The linearity of the model allows for solving the SE very accurately in Real-Time (RT) with a sub-second time resolution. The proposed method is validated numerically and experimentally on the hybrid AC/DC network built at the EPFL.

The real-time centralised optimal control algorithm uses these fast-updated states. Extended load flow equations are recalled to model the hybrid AC/DC network constraints for different control strategies of the AFE. Next, a novel analytical method is presented to compute the sensitivity coefficients of hybrid AC/DC networks, i.e. the partial derivatives of the voltage with respect to the control variables ($P_{ac}, Q_{ac}, V_{dc}, P_{dc}$). The sensitivity coefficients are used in the OPF problem to model the grid voltage and ampacity constraints. Since the sensitivity coefficients are only a function of the grid topology and the grid state, which is updated by the real-time SE, the analytical method enables a sub-second time resolution computation. A numerical validation is included to show the correctness of the analytical solution.

Future work will focus on the experimental validation of the OPF where the optimal setpoints of the AFEs and multiple resources are computed in real-time to maximise different objectives. The results of these experiments will be studied and included in the deliverables of Task 6.2 and Task 6.5.

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Appendix

Kalman Filter

The Discrete KF relies on a measurement model and a process model (Abur & Exposito, 2004). The measurement model \mathbf{H} relates the states variables \mathbf{x} to the measurements \mathbf{z} . The measurement noise is assumed to be uncorrelated, unbiased, white and Gaussian with \mathbf{R} the measurement noise covariance matrix. For the system to be observable, \mathbf{H} needs to be full rank.

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_k + \epsilon, \quad p(\epsilon) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{R}) \quad (92)$$

The process model accounts for the time evolution of the system states. An ARIMA (0, 1, 0) model (Debs & Larson, 1970) is used, which is very suitable for high-resolution measurements where the state between two consecutive time-steps does not change significantly. Because PMUs and DMUs are used that give newly updated synchrophasors every 20 ms, this assumption is valid. The process noise is assumed to be uncorrelated, unbiased, white and Gaussian with \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} the process noise covariance matrix.

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \mathbf{w}_{k-1}, \quad p(\mathbf{w}_{k-1}) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}) \quad (93)$$

Using (92) and (93), the linear KF equations are:

Prediction step:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1} \quad (94)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{k-1} + \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \quad (95)$$

Estimation step:

$$\mathbf{K}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k \mathbf{H}^T (\mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}_k)^{-1} \quad (96)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \quad (97)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_k = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{H}) \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k \quad (98)$$

\mathbf{K}_k is the optimal Kalman gain, namely the value that minimizes the covariance of the estimation error, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$ is the predicted state vector and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ the estimated states. $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k$ and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_k$ are the covariance matrices of the prediction and estimation errors and are defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_k^T] \quad (99)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_k = \mathbb{E}[\hat{\mathbf{e}}_k \hat{\mathbf{e}}_k^T], \quad (100)$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_k = \mathbf{x}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$ and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_k = \mathbf{x}_k - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$. \mathbb{E} denotes the expected value. These relations are the hypothesis that are verified to validate the hybrid KF.

The innovation \mathbf{y}_k (101) is defined as the difference between the measurement and the reconstructed measurements using the predicted state. Its covariance matrix is defined as (102).

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k \quad (101)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_k = \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_k \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}_k \quad (102)$$

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